

Speed-torque relationship for self-tapping bone screw insertion

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Abstract: Bone screws are used for fixing implants and stabilizing fractures. Correct torquing of these screws is important for positive patient outcomes. A previously proposed model-based system may increase the accuracy of bone screw insertion, but this depends on the accuracy of the model. This paper investigates the effects of screw insertion speed on the accuracy of current models by inserting screws 4 times at 15 RPM and 4 at 45 RPM. The 15 RPM speed required notably less torque than the 45 RPM one. Therefore, the effects of insertion speed should be incorporated into current models to improve their accuracy.

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I. Introduction

Bone screws are commonly used in orthopedic surgery to fix implants in place or stabilize fractured bones. Over- or under-torquing these screws can lead to thread stripping or insufficient fixation, respectively; both effects may cause implant failure and/or tissue damage, potentially leading to additional complications or necessitate revision surgery. Hence, correct torquing of bone screws is important for positive patient outcomes.[1]

Bone screws are often tightened in an ad-hoc manner. This is generally successful, but misjudgment may result in inappropriate tightening torques. Varying surgeon skill and experience levels may lead to additional inconsistencies[1]. It has been proposed that a model-based method can be used to identify the material properties of bone during the screw insertion process[2], and that these properties can then be used to recommend or enforce optimal insertion torques. If successful, this could increase the probability of positive patient outcomes and reduce fixation failures.

Two main formulations have been suggested so far from this research. Wilkie et al.[2] proposed a very simple lumped parameter model, which was later expanded[3]. The first model[2] assumed a viscous friction force for the screw insertion, however this was removed later[3], and replaced with the assumption that the torque and speed were independent, due to the lack of evidence for this in literature. It was acknowledged that further work was required to test this, which will be addressed in this work.

This paper covers some initial testing on the relationship between speed and insertion torque. This establishes whether some relationship exists and makes suggestions for future work in this area.

II. Methods

To test the relationship of the screw torque and speed, screws were inserted into a test material, and the material properties were identified from the data using a model.

II.I. Modelling/Parameters

The model used was based on the model developed in Wilkie et al. [3]. However for simplification, the elastic effects were neglected[1,3], making the model closely resemble the precursor model from Seneviratne et al. [4]. This simplification allowed the complex simulated annealing parameter identification[1] to be replaced with a simple linear least squares methodology. The model is summarized in eqn. 1: μ is the friction coefficient[N/N]; σ_{uts} is the bone/material strength [Pa]; α is the angular length of the thread cutting portion of the screw[rad]; T_z is the insertion torque [Nm] of the screw with inserted angular length ϕ [rad]; and G_1 [m³] and G_2 [m³/rad] are geometric parameters dependant on the shape of the screw and hole, relating to the cutting and friction components of torque, respectively.

$$T_z(\phi) = \sigma_{uts}G_1 + \mu\sigma_{uts}\left(\phi + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right)G_2 \quad (1)$$

The screw used was an HB65 screw as shown in ISO 5835:1991 [5]. As the shape of the thread is not a standard triangle, approximations were made to match the model parameters. The thread angle used was $30^\circ(\alpha + \beta)$ [6], and the major diameter was 6.5mm, with a hole size of 3.0mm.

II.II. Data Collection

The screws were driven into bone mimicking[6] rigid polyurethane (PU) foam (SikaBlock® M80, Sika Services AG) at a constant velocity by a closed loop stepper motor system (34HS46-6004D-E1000 with CL86T, OMC CORPORATION LIMITED). A torque sensor (NCTE-2300-20-1-AU-0-0, NCTE AG) was inline in the shaft and was used to record the angular displacement and torque at

100 Hz. The motor and sensor were mounted on a sliding platform with linear bearings, so that it could freely slide as the screw was inserted, while the test material was clamped so that the screw was colinear with the pre-drilled hole. A new hole was used for each experiment. The test rig was placed at a slight incline so that the platform would slide towards the test piece with minimal force, facilitating the engagement of the screw in the hole.

Eight insertions were performed. Four at 15 RPM, and four at 45 RPM. For each test, the screw was inserted for 11 revolutions (approx. 30 mm), then fully removed; this is equal to the threaded length of the screw.

II.III. Data Analysis

The data from the screw insertions was processed with MATLAB. The data was trimmed to the period of the screw insertion, and the zero error of the angular displacement was manually corrected. The estimated material strength for each test was identified using the previously mentioned model though least-squares parameter identification, and the distributions were plotted for the two speeds.

III. Results and discussion

The distributions for the identified strength values at the two speeds are shown in fig. 1. The mean identified strengths for the different insertion speeds are statistically different (Two-sample *t*-test $P < 0.05$). Hence, there is a relationship between identified strength and insertion speed; and because identified strength is proportional to torque (eqn. 1), the torque is also related to insertion speed.

Figure 1. Distribution of identified strength values at 15 and 45 RPM insertion speeds.

The results here suggest strongly that the insertion torque increases with rotational speed. However, the nature of this increase should be determined with higher resolution speed steps. The exact torque-speed relationship could follow several curves. Furthermore, the broader applicability of this research is limited by using PU foam, an often used but imperfect substitute for real bone. A future step in validating this model is testing on ex-vivo animal bone.

There may be several underlying phenomena that could explain this result. A simple example could be viscous friction, which has been previously suggested [2]. A more advanced explanation could be that the material abrades

during the screwing process, reducing the friction stress, and this may be dependent on speed. Another possibility is that the stress built up in the screw threads may reduce over time, so inserting a screw quickly exposes the screw to maximum friction forces, whereas slow insertion allows the frictional forces on the first-formed threads to decrease and reduce friction torque at the end of the screw insertion; this may be the case in bone, as it is known to relax for a short time (~1 min.) after being stressed [7]. Higher heat retention from fast insertion could also have an effect. Future work may consider controlling some of these factors to quantify the lumped effects of the uncontrolled ones, and identify which factors are most significant for incorporation into future models.

The implications of speed-torque relationship are that modelling should consider the time variable as well as the displacement variable. This was done originally in Wilkie et al. [2], but was removed from later models due to a lack of evidence in literature. Considering the time dependence will lead to a more robust model of the screw insertion process and may increase their accuracy.

IV. Conclusions

The speed dependence of self-tapping screw insertion torque was tested, and it was found that in these circumstances, insertion at 45 RPM required more torque than insertion at 15 RPM. More work is required to quantify the exact relationship between torque and insertion speed. Future work may also narrow down the cause of this effect and inspire modelling improvements.

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